

Supplemental Material

Exploring axial muscle performance with the supine bridging activity across critical illness recovery: A prospective observational study

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Table S1. Definition of the supine bridge activity scoring

Six-point ordinal scale based on MRC-SS scoring

0 = No muscle contraction when trying

1 = Visible/palpable muscle contraction but no pelvis lifting

2 = Lifting pelvis without reaching the final position for 5 seconds

3 = Lifting pelvis and reaching final position for at least 5 seconds

4 = Lifting pelvis and reaching final position for 6-15 seconds

5 = Lifting pelvis and reaching final position for more than 15 seconds

Abbreviations: MRC-SS, Medical Research Council Sum Score.

Figure S1. Graphical representation of the supine bridging activity scoring (A) and real images of the initial (B) and final position (C).

Table S2. In-bed physical performance according to walking and sit-to-stand ability on awakening*

In-bed physical measurements on awakening	Ability to walk on awakening*			Ability to sit-to-stand on awakening**		
	Unable to walk (n=21)	Able to walk (n=12)	p-value	Unable to sit-to-stand (n=12)	Able to sit-to-stand (n=21)	p-value
Free supine bridge activity score, median [IQR]	1 [1-2]	2 [2-5]	0.02	1 [1-2]	2 [2-5]	<0.001
Lifting time, sec, median [IQR]	11.0 [7.0-19.0]	23.5 [16.5-38.0]	0.016	9.5 [7.0-14.5]	21.0 [12.0-36.0]	0.004
MRC Sum Score, median [IQR]	36 [28-45]	50 [44-55]	0.009	31 [28-36]	50 [43-55]	<0.001
Proximal muscles score, median [IQR]	2.5 [1.5-3.3]	3.8 [3.4-4.1]	0.01	2.0 [1.1-2.6]	3.8 [3.3-4.0]	<0.001
Distal muscles score, median [IQR]	3.3 [3.0-4.0]	4.5 [3.9-5]	0.007	3.0 [2.4-3.4]	4.5 [4.0-5.0]	<0.001
FSS-ICU (Rolling item 0-7 points), median [IQR]	3 [2-4]	5 [4-7]	0.01	2 [1-3]	5 [4-6]	<0.001

*Ability to walk = Walking FSS-ICU item >2; and inability to walk = Walking FSS-ICU item ≤2

**Ability to sit-to-stand = Sit to stand transfer FSS-ICU item >1; and inability to sit-to-stand = Sit to stand transfer FSS-ICU item ≤1

Abbreviations: IQR, interquartile range; MRC, Medical Research Council; FSS-ICU, Functional Status Score for the Intensive Care Unit